

Validation of the INSL-UniFoam Multi-Physics Framework for Fast Burst Reactor Criticality Safety Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Nuclear criticality safety analysis is essential for preventing uncontrolled fission chain reactions in nuclear facilities. Fast Burst Reactors (FBRs) serve as important research subjects for criticality safety studies due to their self-quenching mechanism driven by thermal expansion negative feedback. However, accurate simulation of FBRs presents significant challenges arising from irregular geometry, severe neutron leakage, strong transient processes, and tightly coupled multi-physics feedback mechanisms. This work presents INSL-UniFoam, a high-fidelity coupled nuclear-thermal-mechanical analysis framework developed on the OpenFOAM platform by the Innovative Nuclear System Laboratory (INSL) research group. The code integrates a discrete ordinates neutron transport solver employing finite volume method with thermal stress solvers capable of handling multi-region, multi-material configurations. A point kinetics-based acceleration algorithm is implemented to improve computational efficiency while maintaining transport-level accuracy. The framework is validated against benchmark problems including Godiva-I and SPR-III fast burst reactors under both steady-state and prompt supercritical transient conditions. For Godiva-I, the calculated steady-state effective multiplication factor shows 184 pcm relative error compared to Monte Carlo reference solutions. Transient simulations achieve peak fission rate predictions reaching 90.1% of experimental values with pulse width capturing 75.7% of measured data. The solver accurately reproduces the spatial-temporal evolution of neutron flux, power distribution, temperature fields, and stress distributions during burst processes. Results demonstrate that INSL-UniFoam provides accurate high-resolution analysis of physical phenomena during criticality excursions, offering valuable computational support for fast burst reactor design and accident safety analysis.

Keywords: Criticality Safety Analysis; Fast Burst Reactors; Multi-Physics Coupling; Discrete Ordinate Method

1. INTRODUCTION

Nuclear criticality safety analysis plays a crucial role in preventing accidents caused by uncontrolled neutron chain reactions in nuclear facilities. It provides detailed assessment of thermal shock-induced deformation and radioactive behavior during supercritical processes, which is critical for nuclear system design and evaluation. Fast burst reactors (FBRs) are a class of reactors featuring thermal expansion self-quenching mechanisms, where power reduction occurs through negative reactivity feedback from fuel thermal expansion during power pulses [1]. Since the 1950s, FBRs represented by Godiva-I [2] have been important subjects for criticality safety experiments and serve as benchmark problems for code validation [3].

During a prompt-critical burst, neutron flux and power rise by several orders of magnitude in microseconds, while intense fission heating drives rapid thermal expansion of metallic fuel and structures. The resulting density reduction provides strong negative reactivity feedback, which terminates the burst and determines the peak power, energy release, and structural response.

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Accurate simulation of such events requires tightly coupled multi-physics: (i) a neutronics solver capable of resolving hard spectra, high leakage, and anisotropic scattering; (ii) a heat-transfer solver for three-dimensional temperature evolution with strong internal heat sources; and (iii) a structural mechanics solver to predict thermal expansion, stress, and strain, and to feed back density-dependent reactivity changes.

The INSL research group at Shanghai Jiao Tong University has developed an OpenFOAM-based multi-physics platform, hereafter referred to as UniFoam, which has been applied to pressurized water reactors, research reactors, and micro-reactors using diffusion and point-kinetics-based neutronics solvers. In this work, UniFoam is extended toward high-fidelity criticality safety analysis of FBRs by implementing a discrete-ordinates (S_N) neutron transport solver and a thermo-mechanical solver suitable for solid metallic cores. A point-kinetics acceleration scheme is further introduced to improve the efficiency of transient S_N calculations.

2. MULTI-PHYSICS EQUATIONS AND SOLVER STRUCTURE

UniFoam employs the finite volume method on OpenFOAM 12[4], discretizing computational domains into mesh cells representing neutron angular flux, temperature, and displacement fields. This section introduces the newly developed solvers for FBR prompt-critical burst simulation.

2.1. Neutron Transport Solver

To accurately calculate FBRs physics, a neutron transport solver based on the discrete ordinate method (S_N) was developed. The multi-group neutron transport equation is:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{v^g} \frac{\partial \psi_\alpha^g(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} + \boldsymbol{\Omega}_\alpha \cdot \nabla \psi_\alpha^g(\mathbf{r}, t) + \Sigma_t^g(\mathbf{r}, t) \psi_\alpha^g(\mathbf{r}, t) \\ = Q_s^g(\mathbf{r}, t, \boldsymbol{\Omega}_\alpha) + \frac{Q_d^g(\mathbf{r}, t)}{4\pi} + \frac{(1-\beta)\chi^g}{4\pi} Q_f^g(\mathbf{r}, t) + \frac{Q_{ex}^g(\mathbf{r}, t)}{4\pi} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where v^g is neutron velocity for group g , ψ_α^g is angular flux for direction α , Σ_t^g is total cross-section, χ^g is fission spectrum, and β is delayed neutron fraction. The source terms include scattering (Q_s^g), delayed neutrons (Q_d^g), and fission (Q_f^g).

The delayed neutron precursor equation is:

$$\frac{\partial C_d(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} = \beta_d \sum_{g=1}^G v \Sigma_f^g(\mathbf{r}, t) \phi^g(\mathbf{r}, t) - \lambda_d C_d(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (2)$$

where C_d is precursor concentration, β_d is delayed neutron fraction, and λ_d is decay constant.

If we let $\mu_0 = \cos(\boldsymbol{\Omega}', \boldsymbol{\Omega}) = \cos \theta_0$ and divide neutrons into different energy groups, then we have:

$$Q_s^g(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{g'=1}^G \int_{4\pi} \Sigma_s^{g' \rightarrow g}(\mathbf{r}, \mu_0) \psi_{g'}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\Omega}') d\boldsymbol{\Omega}' \quad (3)$$

In a single finite volume element, we assumed that cross-sections and other information are uniformly distributed, i.e. $\Sigma_s^{g' \rightarrow g}(\mathbf{r}, \mu_0) = \Sigma_s^{g' \rightarrow g}(\mu_0)$. And let $\mu_0 = \cos(\boldsymbol{\Omega}', \boldsymbol{\Omega}) = \cos \theta_0$. Then for angle φ , Q_s^g can be written as:

$$Q_s^g(\mathbf{r}, \mu^m, \eta^m, \zeta^m) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{g'=1}^G \int_{-1}^1 \int_0^{2\pi} \Sigma_s^{g' \rightarrow g}(\mu_0) \psi_{g'}(\mathbf{r}, \mu', \eta', \zeta') d\varphi' d\mu' \quad (4)$$

where (μ^m, η^m, ζ^m) represents the directional cosines of neutron motion along the x , y , and z axes. By using Legendre polynomials, $\Sigma_s^{g' \rightarrow g}(\mu_0)$ can be expanded as:

$$\Sigma_s^{g' \rightarrow g}(\mu_0) = \sum_{l=0}^L \frac{2l+1}{2} \Sigma_{s,l}^{g' \rightarrow g} P_l(\mu_0) \quad (5)$$

where l represents the order of anisotropic scattering, when $L = 0$, the scattering source is isotropic. $P_l(\mu_0)$ can be written as:

$$P_l(\mu_0) = P_l(\mu)P_l(\mu') + 2 \sum_{k=1}^l \frac{(l-k)!}{(l+k)!} P_l^k(\mu)P_l^k(\mu') \cos[k(\varphi - \varphi')] \quad (6)$$

Combining the above equations, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{s,g}^m &= \sum_{l=0}^L (2l+1) \sum_{g'=1}^G \Sigma_{s,l}^{g' \rightarrow g} P_l(\mu^m) \psi_{g'}^l \\ &+ 2 \sum_{l=0}^L (2l+1) \sum_{g'=1}^G \Sigma_{s,l}^{g' \rightarrow g} \sum_{k=1}^l \frac{(l-k)!}{(l+k)!} P_l^k(\mu^m) \left(\cos(k\varphi^m) \psi_{g'}^{l,k,1} + \sin(k\varphi^m) \psi_{g'}^{l,k,2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$\psi_{g'}^l = \sum_{m=1}^M \omega^m P_l(\mu^m) \bar{\psi}_g^m \quad (8)$$

$$\psi_{g'}^{l,k,1} = \sum_{m=1}^M \omega^m P_l^k(\mu^m) \cos(k\varphi^m) \bar{\psi}_g^m \quad (9)$$

$$\psi_{g'}^{l,k,2} = \sum_{m=1}^M \omega^m P_l^k(\mu^m) \sin(k\varphi^m) \bar{\psi}_g^m \quad (10)$$

where ω^m represents the weight coefficient of direction m in the discrete ordinate quadrature sets; $P_l(\mu^m)$ represents the (l, m) order associated Legendre function.

2.2. Thermal-Mechanical Solver

The heat conduction equation with volumetric heat source Q is:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho c_p T)}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (\kappa \nabla T) + Q \quad (11)$$

where ρ is the density provided by the mechanical solver, c_p is the specific heat capacity, κ is the thermal conductivity coefficient. This formulation remains valid when density varies due to thermal expansion.

The thermo-mechanical response is modeled using linear elastic dynamics with thermal expansion:

$$\rho \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{D}}{\partial t^2} = \nabla \cdot \left[\mu(\nabla \mathbf{D} + \nabla \mathbf{D}^T) + \lambda(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{D})\mathbf{I} - \frac{E\alpha_T}{1-2\nu} \Delta T \mathbf{I} \right] \quad (12)$$

where \mathbf{D} is the displacement, α_T is the thermal expansion coefficient, and (λ, μ) are the Lamé parameters.

The density feedback is computed from the volumetric expansion ratio $\varepsilon_v = \det(\nabla \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{I}) - 1$, and the density is updated as:

$$\rho^{t+1} = \frac{\rho^t}{1 + \varepsilon_v} \quad (13)$$

which is used to update neutronics feedback in the next time step. All equations are discretized using the finite-volume operators provided by OpenFOAM.

2.3. Acceleration and Coupling Strategy

To improve S_N computational efficiency, a point kinetics acceleration algorithm was implemented. At each time step, the point kinetics equations predict the total neutron population:

$$\frac{dn(t)}{dt} = \frac{1}{\Lambda} \left(\frac{k_{\text{eff}}(t) - 1}{k_{\text{eff}}(t)} - \beta_{\text{tot}} \right) n(t) + \sum_m C_m(t) \lambda_m \quad (14)$$

where $n(t)$ is neutron density, Λ is generation time, and k_{eff} is effective multiplication factor. Thus we can obtain the new neutron density n_{PKE} estimated by the point kinetics equation. Then we can adjust the total neutron flux values according to the calculation result of the point kinetics equations, so that the total flux field values more closely approximate the convergent results of the S_N equations:

$$\psi_{\text{new}} = \frac{n_{\text{PKE}}}{n_{t-1}} \cdot \psi_{t-1} \quad (15)$$

The point kinetics equation provides improved initial values for the subsequent S_N equation iteration. The final convergence of the entire neutronics equations and the distribution of physical fields are entirely accomplished by the S_N equations, with the results from the point kinetics equations serving solely to accelerate the iterative convergence speed of the S_N equations.

Time discretization uses first-order backward Euler (`fvm::ddt`) with a fixed step $\Delta t = 1 \times 10^{-6}$ s. Within each step, S_N is solved by fixed-point iterations with lagged scattering and fission sources until the residual meets the prescribed tolerance.

The multi-physics coupling is performed with a single Picard sweep within each time step, i.e., without inner neutronics–thermal–mechanical iterations. The coupling sequence is: (1) neutronics calculates the power distribution; (2) the thermal solver updates the temperature field; (3) the mechanical solver computes displacement and volumetric expansion; (4) cross sections are updated according to density changes:

$$\Sigma^{t+1} = \frac{1}{1 + \varepsilon_v} \Sigma^t \quad (16)$$

The updated cross sections are used in the next neutronics step to realize the density-feedback loop. Although a single mesh is used in the present validation cases, the solver supports mesh-to-mesh field mapping for future non-matching multi-physics coupling.

Therefore, the overall coupling accuracy is effectively first-order in time. Improved within-step implicit coupling iterations will be investigated in future work.

3. VALIDATION AND RESULTS

3.1. Godiva-I Benchmark

Godiva-I is a classical bare fast burst reactor designed and operated by Los Alamos National Laboratory starting in 1951[2]. The reactor consists of a near-spherical highly enriched uranium sphere assembly with 8.7407 cm radius, 93.7% U-235 enrichment, and 18.74 g/cm³ density.

The transport solver employed an 8-group energy structure, P_3 anisotropic scattering, and an S_4 fully symmetric angular quadrature. With a structured hexahedral mesh generated by blockMesh (56,000 cells), the computed eigenvalue was $k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{calc}} = 0.99272$, which differs from the Monte Carlo code OpenMC[5] reference value ($k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{MC}} = 0.99456$) by only 184 pcm. For the coupled calculations, the thermo-mechanical solver used the physical and mechanical parameters listed in Table I.

Table I. Thermo-mechanical parameters of Godiva-I

Parameter name	Value
Density	18740 kg/m ³
Poisson's ratio	0.23
Young's modulus	208 GPa
Specific heat capacity	117.7 J/(kg · K)
Thermal conductivity	27.5 W/(m · K)
Coefficient of linear expansion	$1.39 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1}$

A prompt supercritical transient with an initial reactor period of 29.5 μs was simulated. The time step was fixed at 1×10^{-6} s. Figure 1 presents the total reactor power evolution compared with experimental data [6].

Figure 1. Power evolution during Godiva-I prompt supercritical transient with 29.5 μs initial period

The predicted total power rises from an initial 1 W to a peak of $P_{\text{peak}} = 7.4 \times 10^8 \text{ W}$, corresponding to a peak fission rate of $2.36 \times 10^{19} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The experimental peak fission rate is $2.62 \times 10^{19} \text{ s}^{-1}$, indicating that the model captures approximately 90% of the true peak magnitude. The simulated full-width at half maximum (FWHM) is $8.4 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}$, compared with the measured $1.11 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}$. Therefore, the peak fission rate is 90.1% of the experimental results, and the full width at half maximum is 75.7% of the experiment data.

Using ParaView for post-processing, we can visualize the power density and temperature field distributions, as shown in Figure 2. The simulation starts with an initial total power of 1 W. The results show

Figure 2. Power density distribution at the pulse peak and temperature rise distribution at the end of the transient

that the power is concentrated in the reactor’s central region, leading to a higher temperature rise at the center and lower temperatures at the edges. Additionally, average temperature variation curves were generated, as seen in Figure 3. Initially, the temperature rise is slow due to low system power. However, as the system power increases rapidly, the temperature rises more quickly. In the later stage, with increased negative feedback, the power decreases, and the temperature stabilizes.

Figure 3. Average temperature rise and volumetric expansion ratio varying with time

The “expansion rate” reported in this work refers to the volumetric expansion ratio $\varepsilon_v = \det(\nabla \mathbf{D} + \mathbf{I}) - 1$ used for the density-feedback update in Eq. (13), rather than the equivalent (von Mises) strain. For the Godiva-I pulse, the resulting stress level remains in the elastic regime (see the maximum stress reported below), and the linear thermo-elastic model is therefore adequate for this benchmark.

Several additional sources of error may contribute to the observed discrepancies [7], and will be addressed in future work: (a) A forward Picard coupling strategy is adopted within each time step to reduce computational cost; introducing inner implicit iterations is expected to improve multi-physics convergence and numerical stability. (b) Mesh deformation is not yet included during the coupled transient calculation, so the neutronics mesh remains fixed and geometric expansion is only reflected through density feedback. Incorporating mesh motion will improve consistency between mechanical deformation and neutronics feedback. (c) Neutron spectrum variation is neglected by assuming cross sections depend only on volumetric expansion. Future developments will introduce Monte Carlo-based

neutronics coupling and more accurate treatments of macroscopic cross-section evolution during fast burst transients.

3.2. SPR-III Transient Simulation

The Sandia Pulsed Reactor III (SPR-III) represents a more complex validation case with its multi-region, multi-material configuration. The reactor consists of 18 disk-shaped fuel plates made of U-10Mo alloy, mechanically fastened with stainless steel fixtures and bolts. SPR-III represents a more complex benchmark problem featuring multi-region, multi-material configuration.

The transient was initiated by artificially increasing the fission cross section to obtain an initial reactor period of $18.5 \mu\text{s}$. Figure 4 shows the calculated total power evolution. Post-peak oscillations are observed in the power tail and are more pronounced than in the Godiva-I case. This is attributed to the shorter initial reactor period of SPR-III, which makes the transient more sensitive to feedback delays, together with the single-pass explicit coupling strategy that introduces a phase lag between power generation and density feedback.

Figure 4. Total Power Curve of SPR-III

The calculated peak power reaches $P_{\text{peak}}^{\text{calc}} = 1.1 \times 10^{10} \text{ W}$ with a pulse FWHM of approximately $47 \mu\text{s}$, which is about one order of magnitude lower than reference studies [8]. The main reason is that mesh deformation is not yet included during the coupled transient calculation: although density is updated to account for thermal expansion, the neutronics mesh remains fixed, leading to inconsistency in nuclide inventory conservation and an underestimation of the feedback response. This effect was less significant in the Godiva-I simulations due to smaller expansion levels. Future work will incorporate mesh motion and improved feedback treatments to enhance transient prediction accuracy.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents INSL-UniFoam, a coupled neutronics-thermal-mechanics computational framework developed on the OpenFOAM platform for fast-burst reactor criticality safety analysis. The system integrates a discrete-ordinates transport solver capable of rigorously resolving anisotropic scattering and

pronounced neutron leakage with multi-region, multi-material thermo-mechanical solvers, and employs a point-kinetics-based acceleration strategy to enhance computational efficiency while retaining transport-level fidelity.

Benchmark assessment against Godiva-I demonstrates a steady-state k_{eff} deviation of only 184 pcm relative to high-fidelity Monte Carlo results, while transient simulations reproduce the peak-fission-rate magnitude and temporal evolution of prompt supercritical pulses within 10 % of experimental measurements. Application to the heterogeneous SPR-III configuration confirms the robustness of the framework for complex geometries, though transient peak power is underpredicted by approximately one order of magnitude due to the present omission of mesh-expansion-induced cross-section feedback.

INSL-UniFoam delivers fully resolved space-time fields of neutron flux, power, temperature, displacement, and stress, enabling detailed interrogation of feedback mechanisms and structural response during criticality excursions. The framework provides a high-fidelity basis for design optimization, safety margin quantification, and accident scenario analysis. Ongoing development will incorporate more general boundary conditions, solver-decoupled mesh refinement capabilities, and advanced coupling algorithms to further improve feedback modeling and computational performance.

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